

**EXAMINATION REFORMS IN SCHOOL EDUCATION: NEED,
CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN THE LIGHT OF
NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2016.**

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Abstract

In India, the examination system in school has remained unchanged for so many years. It is stressful and puts burden on the students. The ability of the students is judged on the basis of one annual examination. In this system, performance of the students in one single examination is the sole criterion for success and not success. Scoring more and more marks in exams has become the only aim of students. If this system is better then those who scores high in these exams must be more successful in their life and rest are unsuccessful, but unfortunately it is not true. So there is an urgent need to reforms our current examination oriented school education system and make the examination system that focus on problem-solving, critical thinking and reasoning skills. Such reforms will change the teaching-learning processes and improve learning outcomes. In recent years, Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation has been strengthened so that students are assessed on an ongoing basis for their holistic development, a system of grading in place of marks has been introduced the eliminations of excessive element of chance and subjectivity, de-emphasis on memorization. The objectives are to look at the existing systems and suggest reforms which would help better assessment of students so that they perform well on practical front, marks of any examination won't work there only knowledge will work there. The present study set out to explore the various reforms in the existing examination system as inputs to the New Policy of Education 2016. The Paper explores and suggests various recommendations to bring much needed reforms in the examination systems.

INTRODUCTION

There of course no denying the fact that examination is imperatively necessary for the students. In fact, life itself is a continuous examination but the prevailing system of examination is everywhere an object of criticism. It suffers from a large number of drawbacks and requires complete overhauling. It has failed to deliver the goods and make the education narrow. Successive commission and committees on education have emphasized the need for examination reform and suggested specific measure toward this end. The Mudaliar commission on secondary education (1952-53) also recognized the lack of validity, reliability

and objectivity in examination.

NCF 2005 also emphasized the need for reforms in present examination system by making them child friendly and stress free. Hence it is felt that it is high time that we have a serious look into the issues and bring about some changes by taking of its demerits for making examination an important tool in assessment of child.

CHALLENGES

Detention policy is a challenge: When the students know that they will promote to the next class regardless of their performance in the examination. They become non serious inattentive to studies and irregular in attendance.

Based on rote memory: The Indian examination system is based on rote memory. Questions are asked from the textbook and students who are able to produce what is written in the textbooks, managed to get high scores.

Lack of modern scientific method: There is lack of modern scientific method in our examination system. It hampered the accurate result of large scale of examination like board exams.

Students are only judge by result in board exam: The performance judge only by result in one single annually examination. There is CCE (Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation) but it is not effective as required.

Lack of trained examiner, supervisor, and evaluator: There is lack of trained examiner, supervisor and evaluator in our examination system and their personal bias affect the overall results of the students.

Theoretical aspects given more importance: Our present examination system focus more on mainly theoretical aspects and same time ignore the practical aspect. This may help to pass the examination only but he failed to perform in the practical aspect of subjects.

Corruption and Malpractice in Board exam: The process of examination itself beset with corruption and malpractice papers are leaked copying is rampered and examiner compromise.

Lack of flexibility: There is lack of flexibility in our examination system. Our examination is working on one suit size fit for all the students. This does not cater the needs of all types of the learner.

Granting grace marks to artificially inflate the pass percentage: Many Boards follow the practice of granting the grace marks to students in order to enhance the pass percentage.

Credibility about Evaluation and quality of Board exam: The results of board exam not reflect the reality about the students. The evaluation of a student done entirely on performance in the end of the year examination.

SUGGESTIONS:

Detention policy: Many states have sought a review of the no detention policy be limited up to class fifth but from fifth onwards there must be detention so the students become serious attendative and regular towards their studies.

Culmination of various types of test in the examination: Both objectives and subjective type questions covered the wide area related to teaching and learning that leads to enhance the understanding, analysis and application.

Use of modern tools of evaluation: Scaled scores and percentile or modern scientific method to provide more accurate results and provide comparable results across students.

Strengthening in CCE: There is dire need to strength the CCE. In school education, continuous evaluation is there. But there are a loop holes in comprehensive evaluation. Because both the teachers and parents are giving more importance to academic achievement and completed ignoring the other aspects of personality.

Trained examiner, supervisor and Evaluator: There must be trained examiner, supervisor and evaluator so that examination conducted in a smooth way. In order to lesson the personal bias introduced the recent technology in examination system. There must be provision for training to train the examiner and supervisor to acquaint with the recent techniques and methodology of evaluation.

Equal importance given to practical aspect: Equal importance should be given to practical aspect of subject so that after completing the school education students better adjust practical aspects of life.

Examination body must be accountable: Examination should be conduct in a fair, transparent manner those who involve in corruption or malpractice serious action under rule should be taken against them. Examination system need to transparent, objective placing due emphasizing on analysis understanding and cogent writing skill.

Assessment capacity: Assessment capacity in CBSE and state examination board need to be strengthened.

Developing appropriate questions: Teacher and Educator need to be trained in developing appropriate question for evaluating learning capability and performance of the students.

On demand Board exam: On demand board exam should be introduce to offer flexibility and reduce year end stress of students and parents.

Discontinuing grace marks: The practice of granting grace marks should be discontinued.

The evaluation of students should not depend on performance of only final examination: Weight age need to be given to performance in periodic test, classroom participation quality

of assignments throughout the year for which objective and transparent criteria need to be laid down.

CONCLUSION

From the above suggestions, challenges and needs, it is discovered that the examination system is the most important organ of the education system which require serious reforms. It should be recognized that examination reforms has the potential to lead to education reforms because the education objectives only realize, when our examination is effective. Our examination system must focus on practical knowledge rather than getting good scores in examination.

References

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